

COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT APPROACHES OF ANALYSIS OF WATER DISTRIBUTION NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Water supply networks have been existing since 15th century B.C. and are continuously evolving towards betterment. A water supply network is assessed on its efficiency and capability to cater to the demand of consumers. There are two approaches for analysing a water supply network viz. Demand Driven Approach (DDA) & Pressure Driven Approach (PDA). Conventionally, water supply networks are designed with DDA. This approach is efficient for designing and modelling. It assumes that the demands at all nodes are always satisfied, irrespective of the available nodal pressure. But many a times, in an operational network, certain situations such as pipe burst, pump failure, source failure, fire demand, supply shortage etc. arise. These situations cause pressure deficiency or even negative pressures. Such lower or negative pressures cause deficiency of water at delivery points or sometimes even supply disruption. This is where DDA fails. PDA is comparatively a new approach. But it is capable of simulating pressure deficient conditions and analysing their effects on the network. Though, it is not used for designing, but it can be efficiently used to simulate different conditions, analyse their effects and Figure out solutions to mitigate hazards. This paper compares DDA & PDA by analysing a 7 looped network. The paper also describes the pressure deficient analysis carried out on a District Metered Area (DMA) of a municipal network by simulating critical pipe burst condition and proposes a feasible and economical solution. It will help improve network performance in unfavourable situations.

Keywords: *Water distribution modelling, Pressure dependent demands, NHFR.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is the basic amenity of life, is finite and precious. It is extremely important to use the water wisely and efficiently and satisfy the demands of customers. Water distribution networks are quintessential infrastructure of a growing and developing economy. The prime objective of water distribution networks is to provide water at enough pressures and quantity to all its users. Therefore, water utilities seek to provide customers with safe, reliable, and continuous supply of high-quality water while minimizing costs to improve economic productivity and improve public health. This water is often delivered through complex distribution systems. The performance of these systems is often difficult to understand not only because of their size and complexity, but also because of the large amount of system information and data needed. Hence proper planning and designing of water distribution system is very much essential.

There are two approaches to analyse water distribution networks, viz. Demand driven approach and Pressure driven approach.

1.1 Demand Driven Approach

Conventionally, the design and analysis of water distribution networks is “demand driven”. This approach assumes that demand/discharge at a junction remains constant irrespective of the residual pressure at that junction. This approach is suitable as planning, designing, revamping or re- organisation of networks is easier. But practically, in a real operational network number of situations such as pipe break, pipe replacement, pump failure, fire demand, source failure etc. may arise, which can cause

pressure deficiency in the network. This is where demand driven approach fails to analyse the impact of such conditions.

1.2 Pressure Driven Approach

Pressure dependent approach assumes that the demands/discharges at a junction depend upon the residual pressure at that junction. According to this approach, demands/discharges increase or decrease with increase or decrease in residual pressures at junctions. It can calculate demand shortages in case of pressure deficiency. Therefore, this approach is very useful to analyse practical situations in the network. Though this approach is not used for designing water distribution networks, it can be efficiently used for simulating and analysing pressure deficient condition.

This paper aims to study demand driven approach and pressure driven approach and to compare their results for a given network.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The primary aim of this study is to observe behaviour of network under pressure deficient condition. A benchmark network having 7 loops (Figure 1) is used for analysis. The network consists of 13 nodes, 21 pipes and 2 sources. The total system demand is 0.874 m³/s. The details of network are as shown in Table 1.

For validation of software, the network is solved manually with the most commonly used methods are used viz (1) Hardy-Cross method (2) Newton Raphson Method and by using software with conventional demand driven analysis.

Figure 1. Benchmark Network

Table 1. Details specifying characteristics of network pipes

Pipe No	Pipe Length (m)	Diameter (m)	Hazen-Williams coefficient	Pipe No.	Length (m)	Diameter (m)	Hazen-Williams coefficient
1	609.60	0.762	130	11	883.92	0.305	110
2	243.80	0.762	128	12	1371.60	0.381	108

3	1524.00	0.609	126	13	762.00	0.254	106
4	1127.76	0.609	124	14	822.96	0.254	104
5	1188.72	0.406	122	15	944.88	0.305	102
6	640.08	0.406	120	16	579.00	0.305	100
7	762.00	0.254	118	17	487.68	0.203	98
8	944.88	0.254	116	18	457.20	0.152	96
9	1676.40	0.381	114	19	502.92	0.203	94
10	883.92	0.305	112	20	883.92	0.203	92
				21	944.88	0.305	90

Table 2. Details specifying characteristics of network pipes

Node ID	Elevation (m)	Demand (m ³ /s)	Node ID	Elevation (m)	Demand (m ³ /s)
1	27.43	0.0	8	31.39	0.091
2	33.53	0.059	9	32.61	0.0
3	28.96	0.059	10	34.14	0.0
4	32.00	0.178	11	35.05	0.030
5	30.48	0.059	12	36.58	0.030
6	31.39	0.190	13	33.53	0.0
7	29.56	0.178	RES 1	60.96	-
			RES 2	60.96	-

2.1 Hardy-Cross Method

For designing of single loop systems, the Hardy-Cross method was enough. Hardy-Cross perhaps was the first to suggest in 1936 a systematic iterative procedure for network analysis (Pramod Bhawe, 2006). Hardy-Cross method uses two approaches. (1) Method of balancing flows-applies continuity of flow and (2) Method of balancing heads- applies continuity of heads, to iteratively solve for flows in pipe networks.

Assumptions:

1. Only one equation is considered at a time.
2. The effect of adjacent loops is neglected
3. Higher power terms of discharge correction are neglected.

Even though Hardy-Cross method is simple, easy to apply hence, suitable for hand calculations, its greatest drawback is that it required large number of iterations for convergence. The number of iterations increase as the size of network increases. The network shown in Figure 1 is analysed by Hardy-Cross method.

2.2 Newton-Raphson Method

This method overcomes the assumption in the Hardy-Cross network of neglecting the effect of adjacent loops(Pramod Bhawe, 2006). Instead of considering only one correction equation at a time and solving it, this method considers the effect of all adjacent loops and solves all the correction equations simultaneously. Hence the convergence can be achieved in smaller number of iterations. The network shown in Figure 1 is analysed by Newton-Raphson method.

2.3 WaterGEMS

Bentley's WaterGEMS has been widely used in water industry for designing & modelling of Rising mains or Distribution systems. Being highly advanced software, it provides several operations to

analyse a network. WaterGEMS uses Global Gradient Algorithm for analysis of network. It is capable of handling huge data and has advanced features and tools which help user in analysing complex and simple water distribution networks. It performs steady state as well as extended period simulation of hydraulic behaviour within pressurised pipe networks. In present study, the network shown in Figure 1. is analysed in WaterGEMS. It has a feature to analyse the network with Pressure Driven Approach.

In present study, the results for flow in pipe for all three methods are compared and values are found to be almost matching with each other as shown in Figure 4.

Further, pipe burst condition is simulated by closing pipe-3 in WaterGEMS model and the network was analysed by Demand Driven and Pressure Driven Approach.

2.4 Demand Driven Analysis

This is conventional approach of analysis of water distribution network. It assumes that the demands/discharges at nodes will be equal to the required discharge, irrespective of the pressure head at that junction. This approach has been used for designing and analysing water networks for decades. As per the assumption of Demand Driven Analysis, flow at junctions does not have any relation with the pressure head at junctions. Therefore, Flow equation is always satisfied. (Eq 1)

$$Q_{(\text{Available at junction})} = Q_{(\text{Required at junction})} \quad (1)$$

2.5 Pressure Dependent Analysis

The concept of pressure dependent demands entirely based on relation between available pressure head and the resulting discharge. There are number of Nodal Head-Flow Relationships available, proposed by many researchers. However, WaterGEMS has in-built PDD function which is invented by Zheng Yi Wu et.al. (2012) and it uses following Nodal-Head-Relationship:

$$\frac{Q_i^s}{Q_{ri}} = 0 \quad \text{if } H_i \leq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{Q_i^s}{Q_{ri}} = \left(\frac{H_i}{H_{ri}}\right)^\alpha \quad \text{if } H_i < H_t \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{Q_i^s}{Q_{ri}} = \left(\frac{H_t}{H_{ri}}\right)^\alpha \quad \text{if } H_i \geq H_t \quad (4)$$

Where,

Q_i^s = Calculated demand at a node

Q_{ri} = Requested demand or Reference demand at junction

H_i = Calculated pressure head at junction

H_{ri} = Reference pressure at junction

H_t = Threshold pressure

A typical graph showing pressure measured as a percent of a pressure threshold versus demand as a measure of a percent of a reference demand, illustrates a pressure dependent demand curve, as shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. PDD Curve

(Source – Zheng Wu et. al. (2012 PDD Patent Document))

Where,

Reference Demand – Flow required at junction

Threshold Demand – Flow at threshold pressure

Reference Pressure – Pressure required to satisfy required demand

Threshold Pressure - Pressure value after which flow becomes independent of pressure

This function in WaterGEMS allowed in detailed study of pressure deficient condition for number of different scenarios.

For case study, a DMA [District Metered Area] of Water Distribution Network of Ambikapur town, Chhattisgarh (as shown in Figure 3) is selected. The network of Ambikapur consists of many existing pipes, having considerable ages. The aim of the project was Augmentation of Water Supply Network of Ambikapur along with DMA Demarcation. In this study, a DMA of a zone of Ambikapur is analysed by DDA & PDA. The critical link in the network is identified as shown in Figure 3. The situation of pipe burst is simulated by closing the critical link in WaterGEMS and its effect on whole DMA is studied by simulating following cases.

Case I: DDA – Normal Network

Case II: DDA – Critical pipe burst

Case III: PDA – Critical pipe burst

Further, after analysing different options (Figure 7.), an interconnection with adjacent DMA is suggested to tackle this kind of situation in either DMA. This will help in better operations and save the consumers from water disruption.

Figure 3. Critical link in DMA 5 of Zone 11 of Ambikapur

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The network is analysed by Hardy-Cross method, Newton-Rapson method, and WaterGEMS. The values of flow in pipes by all three methods are almost matching. Hence the results obtained from the software are analysed. The following graphs in Figure 4 show comparison of Hardy-Cross method & Newton-Rapson method with WaterGEMS.

Figure 4. Scatter plot for discharge in pipes for H-C, N-R & WaterGEMS

Following Figure 5. shows and compares flows at junctions in normal and pressure deficient conditions by DDA and PDA. Figure 6. shows flows at any 6 junctions out of 117 junctions of DMA 5 by DDA and PDA in normal and critical link burst condition.

Figure 5. Graphical representation of flows at junctions in pressure deficient condition by DDA and PDA

Figure 6. Graphical representation of flows at 6 junctions in DMA 5, in critical pipe burst condition by DDA and PDA

The total demand of the DMA 5 is 3.01 MLD, however, Pressure Driven Analysis shows that there is demand/discharge shortage of 0.556 MLD in DMA 5 due to critical link burst.

There are only 26 junctions out of 117 which have pressure heads equal to or more than the minimum required pressure or reference pressure.

Figure 7. Options for interconnection with adjacent DMA

Out of three options shown in Figure 7, option three (NP-1 with 200 mm diameter) was selected. The following table shows analysis of all three options with different diameters of pipe.

Table 2 Different options for interconnection with adjacent DMA and their analysis

		Solutions			
	Label	Diameter (mm)	Resulting pressure head- minimum (m H2O)	Resulting demands shortage (MLD)	% Junction below reference pressure
Option 1	P-722 (1)	100	7.8	0.042	58%
		150	8.14	0.005	56%

		200	8.17	0	56%
		250	8.17	-0.001	56%
Option 2	P-725 (1)	100	7.77	0.06	63%
		150	8	0.02	58%
		200	8.1	0.01	58%
		250	8.15	0.013	58%
Option 3	NP-1	100	5.5	0.3	72%
		150	9.22	-0.1	46%
		200	11.68	-0.3	3%
		250	13.2	-0.5	0%

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the two approaches of network analysis viz. Demand Driven and Pressure Driven are studied. Software analysis by both approaches is carried out on a benchmark network in WaterGEMS. For case study, a DMA of Ambikapur town in Chhattisgarh is analysed for pressure deficient condition and its effects are observed. A solution is suggested for such conditions. Following are the observed conclusions:

1. Demand Driven Analysis is good for designing a water distribution networks, but it fails to simulate and analyse various pressure deficient conditions in the network.
2. In this work, the Hardy-Cross analysis, Newton-Raphson analysis and WaterGEMS analysis of 7 looped benchmark networks, gave almost same results for flow in pipes.
3. On simulating pipe burst condition in Benchmark Network, around 85% junctions' pressure head dropped below Reference Pressure i.e. 7 m which causes shortage in flow by 0.040 m³/s.
4. Further, from Pressure Driven Analysis of Benchmark Network, it can be inferred that Reference Pressure is an important parameter while analysing network by Pressure Driven Approach.
5. In this project work, a DMA in a zone of Case Study network is analysed and pipe burst, and supply shortage conditions are simulated in the network. The results showed that Demand Driven Analysis is not capable of analysing such conditions.
6. Pipe burst in DMA 5 causes demand shortage of 0.556 MLD. From various options available as a solution to demand shortage by pipe burst, interconnection from DMA 5 to DMA 1 by a 200 mm pipe is suggested. As a result of this, the junctions having pressure heads less than reference pressure are decreased from 85% to 3% and the demands are fully satisfied at almost all junctions.
7. From further analysis, it is observed that, this solution can be used for pipe burst situation in both the DMAs i.e. DMA 1 & 5 for mitigating its effect.
8. Considering two DMAs i.e. DMA 1 and DMA 5 lengthwise, there is only 1.9% cost rise due to adding a new pipe for interconnection.

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